

1 Contamination of frequency magnitude slope (b-value) by quarry blasts: an
2 example for Italy

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16
17 ***Abstract***

18
19 Artifacts often affect seismic catalogues: among them, the presence of man-made
20 contaminations such as quarry blasts and explosions is a well-known problem. Using a
21 contaminated dataset reduces the statistical significance of results and can lead to
22 erroneous conclusions, thus the removal of such non-natural events should be the first
23 step for a data analyst. Blasts misclassified as natural earthquakes, indeed, may
24 artificially alter the seismicity rates and then the b-value of the Gutenberg and Richter
25 relationship, an essential ingredient of several forecasting models.

26

27 At present, datasets collect several useful information beyond the parameters to locate
28 the quakes in space and time, allowing also the users to discriminate natural and non-
29 natural events. However, selecting them from Web Services queries is neither easy nor
30 clear and part of such supplementary but fundamental information can be lost during
31 downloading. As a consequence, most of statistical seismologists ignore the presence in
32 seismic catalog of explosions and quarry blasts and assume that they were not located
33 by seismic networks or in case they were eliminated.

34 We here show the example of the Italian Seismological Instrumental and Parametric
35 Database: what happens when artificial seismicity is mixed with natural one?

36

37

38 **Introduction**

39

40 Data analysis is a fundamental part of science and statistical seismology made
41 important steps forward both in understanding and forecasting earthquake dynamics in
42 the last decades, also thanks to the increasing development of seismic networks and
43 data acquisition techniques. Besides the main parameters (location, time, magnitude),
44 indeed, each event is nowadays also characterized by several additional attributes
45 describing the source as well as the origin of the event itself.

46 Although databases contain an ever-increasing number of the events' properties, some
47 of them might be lost when data are downloaded from the websites using simplified
48 web accesses. We here show the case of the Italian Seismological Instrumental and
49 Parametric Database, ISIDe (ISIDe Working Group, 2007), where the event type
50 (earthquake, quarry blast, explosion etc.) is indicated since 1 May 2012, but such info is

51 lost during direct downloading from the website <http://terremoti.ingv.it> in txt format.
52 Indeed, the user can custom the search in terms of time, magnitude range, location
53 (longitude, latitude and depth) but cannot discriminate the event type
54 (<http://terremoti.ingv.it/en/search>), also because the presence of non-tectonic events
55 in the database is not clearly described in the website itself. As a consequence, non-
56 natural events such as quarry blasts, controlled, experimental and mining explosions,
57 may be processed together with tectonic quakes.

58

59 How does such loss of info impact the statistical analysis? What happens when artificial
60 seismicity is mixed with natural one?

61

62 The maximum magnitude of quarry and mine blasts in Europe is usually assumed to be
63 2.5-3.0 (Gulia, 2010; Giardini et al., 2004), which corresponds to the blast of about 100-
64 500 kg of TNT, assuming the standard energy release of about 4 MJ per kg of TNT and
65 the Gutenberg and Richter energy-magnitude relation. A higher threshold has been
66 observed in US, where the magnitude of quarry and mine blasts can occasionally exceed
67 magnitude 4 (Stump et al., 2002). Having low magnitudes, the non-natural events enrich
68 the number of small earthquakes in a catalog, falsifying the relative portion of
69 microseismicity respect to the higher magnitudes. This might alter the relative
70 earthquake size distribution and then the b-value of the frequency-magnitude
71 relationship by Gutenberg and Richter (1944). The Gutenberg and Richter relationship
72 is a fundamental ingredient of several short-term forecasting models: among them, the
73 Epidemic Type Aftershock Sequence (ETAS) (Ogata, 1988, 1998) that is used in
74 Operational Earthquake Forecasting (e.g. Jordan et al., 2011), the Short-Term
75 Earthquake Probability model (STEP; Gerstenberger et al., 2005) and the Foreshock

76 Traffic Light System (Gulia and Wiemer, 2019; Gulia et al., 2020). Many authors pointed
77 out that the b-value is a proxy of the state of the stress of a region (e.g. Wyss, 1973),
78 being inversely correlated to it and showed the b-value capability to be a “stressmeter”
79 of the Earth’s crust at different scales: from laboratory specimens (e.g., Scholz, 1968) to
80 observations (Schorlemmer and Wiemer, 2005; Schorlemmer et al., 2005; Tormann et
81 al., 2015; Gulia et al., 2010, 2016, 2018; Petruccelli et al., 2018, 2019a, 2019b). The b-
82 value can have a precursory drop before the failure (Papadopoulos et al., 2010; Nanjo et
83 al., 2012; Schurr et al., 2014; Tormann et a., 2015; Gulia et al., 2016; Gulia and Wiemer,
84 2019; Huang et al., 2020) suggesting that the seismicity evolution in terms of b-value
85 should be routinely monitored. Such finding is confirmed in numerous laboratory
86 studies, showing an increasing relative proportion of larger events as the system
87 approaches failure (e.g. Goebel et al., 2013).

88 The higher b-values, resulting from an artificial enrichment of the portion of low-
89 magnitude events in regional catalogs, can mask the spatio-temporal variations, altering
90 the alerts and be misinterpreted as a change in the natural phenomena.

91
92 Long-term models can also be affected by falsified seismic rates and b-values: in the
93 probabilistic seismic hazard assessment (PSHA, usually based on Cornell, 1968), the
94 Gutenberg and Richter relationship defines event rates used to compute expected levels
95 of ground shaking. PSHA, indeed, assumes a Poissonian distribution of seismicity and
96 such requirement is generally satisfied by declustering the input catalog (Gardner and
97 Knopoff, 1974, van Stiphout et al., 2010): for such reason, in the hazard assessment,
98 rates are estimated on declustered catalogs (Field et al., 2014; Petersen et al., 2018;
99 Wiemer et al., 2009). Mizrahi et al. (2021) show that declustering can introduce a
100 systematic bias to the size distribution of earthquakes, potentially biasing hazard

101 assessment and Iervolino (2019) proposes a generalization of the hazard integral to re-
102 introduce aftershocks in PSHA. However, at present, the seismic rates are still estimated
103 on declustered catalogs: once the aftershocks are removed, the relative portion of
104 quarry blasts, if present, increases as these latter usually occur almost uniformly in
105 time, and the b-value of the grid node or zone affected by artificial events, too. As a
106 consequence, the rates of the highest magnitudes are underestimated. Although in Italy
107 the input dataset is usually cut at magnitude 4, in other Countries (e.g. Switzerland;
108 Wiemer et al., 2009) the threshold magnitude cutoff is lower.

109 Stress-based spatiotemporal models, that describe the aftershocks productivity, can
110 also be biased by quarry blasts: the expected rate of earthquakes in a given magnitude
111 range (e.g., Dietrich, 1994) is indeed a function of the background seismicity.

112

113 It is important to note that high b-values can be observed in different natural settings,
114 such as the volcanic regions (e.g., Wyss et al., 1997, 2001; Roberts et al., 2015) as well as
115 in Enhanced Geothermal Systems during the co-injection period (Bachmann et al.,
116 2012) and in hydrocarbon reservoirs during extraction of natural gas (Muntendam-Bos
117 et al., 2017). Being able to discriminate between natural, induced and not-natural b-
118 values can help seismologists to understand and interpret the physical phenomena
119 under investigation.

120

121 For all the reasons above, non-natural events must be identified, mapped, and excluded
122 from the catalogues before any meaningful statistical analysis can be performed.
123 Statistical seismologists use catalogues assuming explosions have been eliminated but,
124 as we showed before in the case of direct download from some websites, such events
125 can erroneously be included in the catalogs.

126

127 Italy is an ideal testing region due to the simultaneous presence of a dense seismic
128 network and several extraction sites. In 2014 the number of mining and quarrying
129 active extraction sites in Italy was equal to 4,612 (<http://www4.istat.it/>) and a detailed
130 map is available at *The Italian Institute for Environmental Protection and*
131 *Research, ISPRA*, website (<https://www.isprambiente.gov.it/en/istitute>) but no
132 information is given on which of them use explosives.

133 Explosives are the primary source of energy for rock breaking in the mining, quarrying
134 and construction industries (Sanchidria'n et al. 2007; Hamdi et al. 2008), particularly
135 for the building materials. Underground mines and blasting are also excavated by
136 explosions as well as salt and coal basins are mined by blasting. Explosives are also
137 largely employed in civil engineering (e.g. tunnel and subway) and in offshore seismic
138 prospecting.

139

140 Wiemer and Baer (2000) proposed a purely statistical tool to identify quarry and mine
141 blasts based on the ratio between daytime to nighttime events (from now on D/N). In
142 the case of all-natural events, such value should be around 1 ideally or more probably
143 slightly lower, due to the lower magnitude detection threshold in nighttime owing to
144 the lower level of anthropic seismic noise. On the contrary, the presence of non-natural
145 events should increase such ratio because mine blasts are usually performed during
146 daytime.

147

148 In this work, we first show the D/N maps performed, by the tool proposed by Wiemer
149 and Baer (2000), for two versions of ISIDE: the one downloaded directly from the
150 Website in txt format and the one downloaded by INGV Web Services

151 (<http://webservices.ingv.it/fdsnws/event/1/>), selecting the event type *earthquake*, in
152 the period 2005-2020. Then, by the comparison with the related b-value maps, we show
153 the correspondence between unusually high b-values in the maps ($b > 1.4-1.5$) to the
154 areas with the highest D/N: the presence of non-natural events, mixed with natural
155 ones, falsifies both the seismic rates and the b-value of the Gutenberg and Richter
156 relationship.

157

158 Gulia (2010) mapped the daytime to nighttime ratio for the available European regional
159 catalogs, highlighting the presence of numerous quarry blasts; among them the Italian
160 Seismicity Catalogue (C.S.I. 1.1; Castello et al. 2006), that contains about 100.000
161 earthquakes during period 1981-2002. From 1 May 2012, the indication of event-types
162 different from *earthquake* is routinely provided by the Italian Seismic Network: we thus
163 repeat the same analysis on the dataset downloaded via Web Service, selecting only the
164 event type *earthquake*: are all the events contained in such version, earthquakes only?
165 Are all the quarry blasts recorded by the network, correctly identified?

166

167

168

Data and Method

169

170 We compute the daytime-nighttime ratio maps (Figure 1 a-d) for different time periods,
171 on a 10-km regularly spaced grid using the events, within a 20-km radius from each
172 node, taken from ISIDe (ISIDe Working Group, 2007). ISIDe contains the parameters of
173 earthquake locations computed by the INGV National Seismic Network since 1985 but
174 as input data for our estimates, we select events from 16 April 2005 (last access on 30
175 November 2020), when the Italian Seismic Network was reorganized and extended and

176 the quality of hypocentral locations and magnitudes was definitely improved, to 30
177 November 2020..

178 The D/N is defined as:

179

$$180 \quad Rq = Nd Ln / Nn Ld. \quad (1)$$

181

182 where Nd is the total number of events in the daytime, Nn in the nighttime period, Ld is
183 the number of hours in the daytime period and Ln in the nighttime period. According to
184 Wiemer and Baer (2000), an indicative value for the anomalous D/N is >1.5 , well
185 highlighted by the implemented color palette that, from around 1.5, abruptly changes
186 from blue-sky to pink shades. We define as *daytime* the hours from 7 a.m. to 6 p.m. and
187 *nighttime* the hours from 6 p.m. to 7 a.m. Note that according to eq. 1 the number of
188 events in each time window are normalized to the number of hours (11 for *day* - Ld - and
189 13 for *night* - Ln -).

190

191 We then establish 3 different time periods:

- 192 • 16 April 2005 - 30 November 2020: the whole dataset downloaded in txt format
193 at <http://terremoti.ingv.it/en/search>;
- 194 • 16 April 2005-30 April 2012, when the event-type info is not yet available:
195 natural and non-natural events are mixed together and indicated with event type
196 *earthquake*; they can be identified only by statistical analysis. Even a dataset
197 downloaded via Web Services, specifying the event type *earthquakes*, is
198 contaminated by non-natural events in the time period preceding May 2012;
- 199 • 1 May 2012 - 30 November 2020: when the even-type info is available. For such
200 time interval, we calculate two maps: one for the events downloaded in txt

201 format from <http://terremoti.ingv.it/en/search> and one selecting only the
202 events identified as “earthquakes” via Web Services
203 (<http://webservices.ingv.it/fdsnws/event/1/>).

204

205 We then calculate the b-value map for the two catalogs (the one containing all the
206 events and the one contained the events classified as *earthquake* only) in the whole
207 period 16 April 2005 – 30 November 2020 (Figure 2 a-b), using the same grid and the
208 same radius adopted in Figure 1 a-d. The magnitude of completeness is estimated at
209 each grid node (*Maximum Curvature*, Wiemer and Wyss, 2000) with a 0.2 correction
210 (Woessner and Wiemer, 2005) and we require a minimum sample size of 50 events
211 above M_c to compute the b-value by the maximum likelihood method. Note that we
212 couldn't estimate a b-value for all the grid nodes with an already associated D/N due to
213 the minimum number of events above M_c required for the b-value.

214 For some of the grid nodes with anomalous D/N, we show the histograms of the hour of
215 the events, that represents a first and effective tool to identify the presence of quarry
216 blasts in a catalog: quarry and mines rich regions, indeed, reveal a typical pattern, with
217 a very large number of events during daytime hours.

218

219 **Results**

220

221 In all the four maps, anomalous high D/N are sparse on the whole Italian territory and
222 most of them have been identified and described in Gulia (2010), corresponding to
223 known excavation districts, such as Apuane-Garfagnana and Fabriano (respectively,
224 areas D and F in Figure 1a; see Table 1 for the list of the excavation districts in Figure
225 1a). The user, in the case of a download in txt format at

226 <http://terremoti.ingv.it/en/search>, would unconsciously download also a big number
227 of non-natural events, that would then be erroneously processed as earthquakes
228 (Figure 1a).

229 Since the event types different from *earthquake* are specified only from 1 May 2012,
230 even a dataset downloaded via Web Services specifying the event type as *earthquake*
231 would be contaminated by non-natural events till such date: Figure 1b shows the D/N
232 map from 2005 to 30 April 2012. Unluckily, copious non-natural events are inevitably
233 downloaded from Web Services in any case also by a user who selects only the event
234 type *earthquake*. The high contaminated regions are about the same of Figure 1a.

235 The last two maps (Figure 1 c-d) show and compare the D/N, in the time period starting
236 from the event type identification (May 2012), for the two catalogs. Here also the
237 contaminated regions are about the same of Figure 1 a-b, but often with a smaller size
238 and value, due to the partial blasts' identification, that somewhat reduces the gap
239 between the number of daily and nighttime events.

240 The similarity between these two maps (2012-2020) compared to the previous period
241 (2005-2012, Figure 1b), indeed, points out the improved capability of the network
242 operators to detect and identify non-natural events in some areas, however a very
243 significant contamination still persists. Before analyzing in detail the most
244 contaminated regions, we compare the D/N maps in Figure 1 with the two b-value maps
245 in Figure 2 a-b, for the whole time period and for the two catalogs: most of the regions
246 with an unusually high b-value (>1.4-1.5) and a corresponding high D/N (>1.5) are well-
247 known active excavations districts. Furthermore, the correspondence between high
248 D/N and high b-values is well represented in Figure 2 c-d, where we plot the D/N and
249 the b-value for all the grid nodes of the maps: the b-values in the range that is usually
250 observed in different natural settings (0.6-1.2/1.3) are well correlated with the typical

251 values of the daytime to nighttime ratio, that is around 1 and lower. On the contrary,
252 unusually high b-values correspond mainly to the highest daytime to nighttime ratios.

253

254 In the Introduction we wonder whether all the quarry blasts recorded by the network
255 are correctly identified: by the observation of the above maps and plots, we may already
256 claim they are not. However, hereafter, we will list and comment in detail the regions,
257 labeled from A to J in Figure 1a, by the analysis of some specific grid nodes with
258 anomalous D/N and the comparison, when possible, with the corresponding b-values,
259 for the time periods 16 April 2005 - 30 April 2012 and 1 May 2012 - 30 November 2020.

260

261 The histograms containing the hour of the day of the total number of the events for the
262 regions A-B-C-E are shown in Figure 3, together with their seismicity maps. The relative
263 daytime to nighttime ratios are displayed too. In these four regions, most of the events
264 have been recorded between 10 a.m. and 3 p.m., with a minimum around the lunch
265 break (e.g., Figure 3 c-d-k-o), as already pointed out in Gulia (2010). The spatial clusters
266 of events locate the active quarries (Castello and Pagagnone, 2016; see also the websites
267 https://www.regione.vda.it/territorio/territorio/attivita_estrattive/cave/cave_authorized_i.aspx;

268 http://www.pianidibacino.ambienteinliguria.it/SV/03centa/varianti/DDG_2019_7664.pdf).

269 In the regions A and B (Figure 3 a-h) the D/N of the second time period, that is
270 when the catalog should contain only earthquakes, is even higher than in the previous
271 one. On the contrary, the D/N in the regions C and E (Figure 3 i-p) decreases with time
272 but remains higher than 1.5, indicating a partial identification of non-natural events;
273 however, the three very restricted, well-defined and isolated spatial clusters in the
274 seismicity map of the grid node in region E (Figure 3n) are the best visual example,
275

276 among the several ones we analyzed, of the highly-suspected non-natural origin of the
277 events. In this grid node, the daytime events have been recorded mostly between 9.55
278 a.m. and 10 a.m. during Spring and Summer and between 10.55 a.m. and 11 a.m. during
279 Autumn and Winter, indicating a one-hour shifted time of the blasting operations due to
280 the daylight-saving time on Spring-Summer in Italy. Such *peculiarity* characterizes also
281 the events in the time period following May 2012, where the quarry blasts should had
282 been identified and classified with the correct *event type* by the network.

283

284 For these four regions, where quarries and mines are active and the natural seismicity
285 is very low, we couldn't calculate and compare the b-values of the two time periods.

286 But what happen in seismically active regions with working quarries and mines? That is
287 the case of the regions labeled as D and F in Figure 4 and G in Figure 5, that are
288 excavation districts, also affected by natural seismicity.

289

290 In Figure 4 we show a seismically active area in Northern Tuscany (area D in Figure 1a):
291 the Apuane-Garfagnana district, that is a well-known excavation district since the age of
292 ancient Romans: the white marble, also known as "white gold", that artists like
293 Michelangelo Buonarroti and Antonio Canova transformed in world heritage
294 masterpieces, was mined here. In the first time period, from April 2005 till the end of
295 April 2012, the events in this small area are spatially clustered (D2) and the histogram
296 of the hour of the events (Figure 4b) shows the typical pattern of quarry rich area: the
297 events are concentrated between 9 a.m. and 11 a.m. In the following time period (from
298 1 May 2012 to 30 November 2020), the events are still spatially clustered (Figure 4f)
299 but towards the North (D1) and the histogram of the hour of the events (Figure 4g)

300 shows now the typical pattern of a slightly contaminated area: the nighttime hours have
301 the highest peaks but there are still peaks around 10 a.m. and 3 p.m. That is due to the
302 simultaneous identification of most of blasts (The D/N of D2 passes from 40 to 1.8, for
303 example; Figure 4 d and i) and to a seismic sequence with a maximum M_L of 4.8 that hit
304 the region on January 2013 (D1): its aftershocks increases the number of events in the
305 grid nodes, that passed from about 30 events per year to 90 whilst the overall b-value
306 decreases from 1.5 (almost all blasts) to 1.1 (blasts and aftershocks; Figure 4e). It is
307 important to note that, in the epicentral area of the M_L 4.8, the D/N remains below 1,
308 even if a very small contamination is clear (hours 11 a.m. and 3 p.m., Figure 4h), in fully
309 agreement with Wiemer and Baer (2000): the detection threshold is generally lower
310 during the day due to the ambient noise and, as a consequence, regions not containing
311 quarries generally show a decrease in the number of events detected during the day and
312 an increase during the night. Thus, we should expect a D/N lower than 1 in the case of
313 natural seismicity and this grid node is a perfect illustration. The same grid node
314 illustrates also the example of non-natural events, in D2.

315 In this region, the b-value results from the mixing of natural and not-natural events:
316 there has been a strong improvement with time and most of blasts are now correctly
317 identified by the network, even if a further effort is required to identify and remove all
318 of them.

319

320 In Figure 4 j-r, we show the case of a grid node in a seismically active area with only low
321 magnitude events (area F in Figure 1a; the Cingoli district, Marche), that is another well-
322 known and wide extraction district of the Country, already described in Gulia (2010). In
323 the seismicity maps (Figure 4 j and n), the events are spatially clustered in few main
324 areas: we here choose two of them, named F1 and F2, to compare the evolution with

325 time of a seismically active area (F1) with an extraction one (F2). Before May 2012, only
326 3 events have been recorded in F1 and more than 80% of the events in the whole grid
327 node occurred during daily hours: the D/N of the node is 5.5 (Figure 4k); after such
328 date, the D/N passes to 0.8, showing a small blast contamination (Figure 4o). The D/N
329 of the natural seismicity in F1 is always below 1, while the D/N in F2 decreases from 70
330 to about 6: as already shown in the previous case, most of blasts are nowadays
331 identified by the network, but several ones still remain.

332 The overall b-value of the events in the grid node, before May 2012, is 1.4 (Figure 4r): a
333 very high value respect to the one expected from this area, considering its prevalent
334 style-of-faulting (Gulia and Wiemer, 2010). After such date, the b-value decreases to 1.2,
335 possibly due to the increment of natural seismicity and the contemporary partial
336 identification of non-natural events. As for the grid node in region D, the overall b-value
337 results from the mixture of natural and non-natural events.

338

339 Figure 5 illustrates two interesting case studies: the first one is about a grid node in the
340 region labeled as G in Figure 1a, Central Italy. Natural and non-natural seismicity are
341 mixed together, as revealed by the histograms of the hour of the events of two small
342 spatial clusters (G1 and G2): before May 2012, 349 events out of 354, in G1, are daytime
343 events and the relative b-value (1.9 in Figure 5e) is unusually high, more than twice that
344 typical, according to Gulia and Wiemer (2010), for the region. The G1 excavation area
345 has been successfully identified after 2012, indeed ISIDE, in the following period,
346 contains only 4 events, 2 during daytime and 2 during nighttime. Few blasts still remain
347 also in the adjacent areas G2; however, this area has been successfully located by the
348 network operators and most of non-natural events identified. The overall b-value
349 decreases to 1.1.

350

351 As well as for the previous case, in the grid node in area H (Figure 5 j-r) most of blasts
352 have been successfully identified: the D/N of the whole area passes from 5 to 1 and the
353 b-value decreases from 1.2 (resulting from many blasts and few natural events) to 0.9
354 (few blasts Figure 5r).

355

356 The last two case studies, shown in Figure 6 (areas labeled as I and J in Figure 1a),
357 exhibit a similar evolution in time. Most of the seismicity before May 2012 is composed
358 by non-natural events: the D/N are, respectively, 2.6 and 43 (Figure 6 b and k) and the
359 b-values 1.7 and 2.2 (Figure 6 e and r), among the highest values in the whole Country.
360 After May 2012, both D/N and b-value decreases, possibly due to the correct but still
361 partial identification of non-natural events.

362

363 Finally, since quarry blasts are performed during the day, the nighttime events should
364 be all tectonic and scale with a lower b-value respect to the daytime events. We then
365 divided the events according to the hour of the day for the above grid nodes with low-
366 magnitude events only and show the comparison of the frequency magnitude
367 distributions for the two periods (Figure 7). The theoretical expected behavior is fully
368 confirmed for all the five nodes: the nighttime b-value are all well below the daytime
369 ones, in some cases less than the half.

370

371 **Discussion and Conclusion**

372

373 Every day, beyond tectonic events, seismic networks detect several non-natural quakes:
374 among them, quarry and mine blasts are the most numerous anthropogenic recorded

375 events. Often, such events are not identified and thus collected together with tectonic
376 events.

377

378 Having low magnitudes, the artificial events enrich the number of small earthquakes in
379 a catalog, contaminating the natural signals and seismicity datasets adulterating the
380 relative portion of microseismicity respect to the higher magnitudes. The resulting
381 seismic rate changes and the relative earthquake size distribution, or b-value of the
382 Gutenberg and Richter relationship (1944), are falsified.

383

384 The natural signal is then contaminated, impacting many short-term forecasting
385 models, such as ETAS (Ogata, 1988, 1998) or the FTLS (Gulia and Wiemer, 2019), where
386 seismic rates and b-value, both inferred from the Gutenberg and Richter relationship,
387 are a basic ingredient.

388

389 Long-term analysis, such as PSHA, can be also impacted by non-natural events: quarry
390 blasts, if present, increase the b-value of the grid node or zone affected by artificial
391 events, resulting in an underestimation of the highest-magnitude rates.

392

393 In this work we show the example of the Italian Seismological Instrumental and
394 Parametric Database, where the *event types* of the non-natural events are available since
395 1 May 2012 only. In the *Custom Search* page (<http://terremoti.ingv.it/en/search>), the
396 user can set the starting and the end date, the Magnitude as well as the
397 Latitude/Longitude and the Depth ranges but the Event Type is not mentioned. Being
398 the event type not available among the *Custom Search* options in ISIDE, the user
399 downloads also non-natural events, not being conscious of this.

400 Other online available catalogs, for example The ANSS Comprehensive Earthquake
401 Catalog (ComCat; <https://earthquake.usgs.gov/earthquakes/search/>) by U.S. Geological
402 Survey (USGS), allows the user to set also the Event Type among the *Advanced Options*.
403 The Event Type option for ISIDE can be set only when retrieving data via Web Services.

404

405 We download and compare two versions of ISIDE: one downloaded at
406 <http://terremoti.ingv.it/en/search> and one via Web Services, specifying the Event Type
407 *earthquake*: are all the non-natural events correctly recognized? If not, how much non-
408 natural events, misclassified as earthquakes, do impact the b-value?

409

410 As a first test, we spatially map the ratio of daytime to nighttime events (D/N),
411 proposed by Wiemer and Baer (2000) to investigate the presence of quarry blasts, for
412 different time-intervals of the two catalogs, showing that:

413

- 414 - in the whole period (16 April 2005 – 30 November 2020) the dataset
415 downloaded at <http://terremoti.ingv.it/en/search> in txt format is heavily
416 contaminated by quarry blasts in the whole Italian territory (Figure 1a);
- 417 - the period 16 April 2005 – 30 April 2012, where the event type is always
418 indicated as *earthquake* and thus the events are common to both catalogs, shows
419 an even wider contamination that can be detected only by statistical analysis
420 (Figure 1b);
- 421 - the following time period, that is 1 May 2005 – 30 November 2020, is still highly
422 contaminated by non-natural events in both catalogs (Figure 1 c-d); however, in
423 the known extraction districts, there is a general improvement for the catalog

424 downloaded via Web Services. Some areas where extractions started after 2012
425 (e.g. area B, Figure 3b) seem to be unknown.

426

427 We then spatially map the b-value for the two catalogs by using the same grid and
428 radius already adopted for the D/N maps (Figure 2 a-b): since we required a minimum
429 number of events above M_c to calculate the b-value, not all the grid nodes with a D/N
430 have a corresponding b-value. The regions with unusually high b-values ($>1.4-1.5$) well
431 correspond to the regions with high D/N in Figure 1. To further highlight the correlation
432 between high b-value and high D/N, we plot the two values for the same grid nodes
433 (Figure 2 c-d), confirming the correspondence.

434

435 Some of the grid nodes with anomalous D/N have been analysed in detail: for such
436 areas, we show the seismicity maps, the histograms of the hour of the events (Figures 3
437 to 6) and, when possible, the frequency magnitude distributions before and after 1 May
438 2012. There has been a general improvement with time and several quarry blasts are
439 now correctly identified by the network's operators, however many ones still remain,
440 affecting the b-value estimations and increasing the portion of low-magnitude events.

441

442 The seismicity of the grid node in Figure 4a-i offers an incisive and clear example of
443 artificial b-value temporal fluctuations due to non-tectonic events: it is an excavation
444 area hit by a Ml 4.8 in 2013. If we compare the frequency magnitude distributions of the
445 two periods (Figure 4e), we note an apparent 27% b-value decrease (from 1.5 to 1.1):
446 according to several forecasting models and to evidence from laboratory specimens,
447 such decrease should suggest a change in the physical condition of the region, resulting
448 somewhat in an alert for an impending strong earthquake.

449

450 Finally, since quarry blasts are performed during the day, we expect that the all the
451 nighttime events are natural quakes: we compare, in Figure 7, the frequency magnitude
452 distributions of daytime and nighttime events for some of the previous analyzed grid
453 nodes with no events with magnitude greater than 3.5: all the daytime b-value are
454 higher than the nighttime ones.

455

456 Our analysis reveals the presence of numerous quarry blasts in the Italian Seismological
457 Instrumental and Parametric Database, ISIDe (ISIDe Working Group, 2007) in the
458 period 16 April 2005 – 30 April 2012, misclassified as earthquakes. After 1 May 2012,
459 there is a general improvement in identifying the event type. However, many quarry
460 blasts are still not correctly classified and such improvement is lost when the user
461 downloads the event list at <http://terremoti.ingv.it/en/search> in txt format.

462

463 **Data and Resources**

464 The Italian Seismological Instrumental and Parametric Database, ISIDe (ISIDe Working
465 Group, 2007), is available at <http://terremoti.ingv.it/en/search> and from INGV Web
466 Services for full download (webservices.ingv.it/fdsnws/event/1/).

467 Both figures and calculations were performed by MATLAB, available at
468 www.mathworks.com/products/matlab.

469

470 **Declaration of Competing Interests**

471 The authors declare no competing interests

472

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483

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676 **Table**

Letter	Excavation District	Material
A	Albiano - Trento	Porphyry
B	Issogne-Gressoney	Green marble, Limestone, Slate
C	Savona	Limestone and Quartzite
D	Apuane-Garfagnana	White, Red and black marble
E	Maremma	Limestone
F	Cingoli-Marche	Limestone
G	Riofreddo	Limestone and Basalt
H	Gargano	Marble and Limestone
I	Altamura-Matera	Limestone and Marble
J	Siracusa	Porphyry and Basalt

677 Table 1 – List of the excavation districts labeled in Figure 1 with the letters A-J and the extracted
678 material.

679 **Figure captions**

680 **Figure 1 A-D.** Maps of the daytime to night-time ratio (D/N): a) for the time interval
681 2005-2020 and for the whole dataset downloaded in txt format at
682 <http://terremoti.ingv.it/en/search>. The letters A-J correspond to the excavation districts
683 listed in Table 1. b) for the time interval 16 April 2005 - 30 April 2012, where the events
684 are classified with event type *earthquake*; c) for the time interval 1 May 2012 - 30
685 November 2020, for all the events downloaded in txt format at
686 <http://terremoti.ingv.it/en/search>; d) for the time interval 1 May 2012 - 30 November
687 2020, for all the events downloaded via Web Services selecting the event type
688 *earthquake* only. The maps are computed on a 10-km regularly spaced grid using the
689 events within a 20-km radius from each node.

690

691 **Figure 2 A-D.** a-b) Maps of the b-value for the time interval 16 April 2005 - 30
692 November 2020, computed on a 10-km regularly spaced grid using the events within a
693 20-km radius from each node for a) the whole dataset downloaded in txt format at
694 <http://terremoti.ingv.it/en/search> and b) the whole dataset downloaded via Web
695 Services selecting the event type *earthquake* only. c-d) plot of the D/N against the b-
696 value for all the grid nodes adopted in the previous maps for c) the whole dataset
697 downloaded in txt format at <http://terremoti.ingv.it/en/search> and d) the whole
698 dataset downloaded via Web Services selecting the event type *earthquake*.

700 **Figure 3 A-P.** Spatial and statistical analysis of four grid nodes in the areas labeled as A-
701 B-C and E in Figure 1a. a-b) Seismicity maps and histograms of the hours of the events
702 (c-d) for a grid in area A for, respectively, the events downloaded at
703 <http://terremoti.ingv.it/en/search> in the period 16 April 2005 - 30 April 2012 and for
704 the events downloaded via Web Services selecting the event type *earthquake* from 1
705 May 2012 - 30 November 2020. e-f) Seismicity maps and histograms of the hours of the
706 events (g-h) for a grid in area B for, respectively, the events downloaded at
707 <http://terremoti.ingv.it/en/search> in the period 16 April 2005 - 30 April 2012 and for
708 the events downloaded via Web Services selecting the event type *earthquake* from 1
709 May 2012 - 30 November 2020. i-j) Seismicity maps and histograms of the hours of the
710 events (k-l) for a grid in area C for, respectively, the events downloaded at
711 <http://terremoti.ingv.it/en/search> in the period 16 April 2005 - 30 April 2012 and for
712 the events downloaded via Web Services selecting the event type *earthquake* from 1
713 May 2012 - 30 November 2020. m-n) Seismicity maps and histograms of the hours of
714 the events (o-p) for a grid in area E for, respectively, the events downloaded at
715 <http://terremoti.ingv.it/en/search> in the period 16 April 2005 - 30 April 2012 and for
716 the events downloaded via Web Services selecting the event type *earthquake* from 1
717 May 2012 - 30 November 2020.

718

719 **Figure 4 A-R.** Spatial and statistical analysis of two grid nodes in the areas labeled as D
720 and F. Grid node in area D in the time period 16 April 2005 - 30 April 2012: a) seismicity
721 map with two spatial clusters, D1 and D2, circled in black; histogram of the hour of

722 events and relative D/N for b) all the events in the grid node, c) all the events in the D1
723 spatial cluster and d) all the events in the D2 spatial cluster. Grid node in area D in the
724 time period 1 May 2012 - 30 November 2020: f) seismicity map with two spatial
725 clusters, D1 and D2, circled in black; histogram of the hour of events and relative D/N
726 for g) all the events in the grid node, h) all the events in the D1 spatial cluster and i) all
727 the events in the D2 spatial cluster. e) frequency magnitude distributions for all the
728 events in the grid node D from 16 April 2005 to 30 April 2012 (blue circles) and from 1
729 May 2012 to 30 November 2020, red asterisks.

730 Grid node in area F in the time period 16 April 2005 - 30 April 2012: j) seismicity map
731 with two spatial clusters, F1 and F2, circled in black; histogram of the hour of events
732 and relative D/N for k) all the events in the grid node, l) all the events in the F1 spatial
733 cluster and m) all the events in the F2 spatial cluster. Grid node in area F in the time
734 period 1 May 2012 - 30 November 2020: n) seismicity map with two spatial clusters, F1
735 and F2, circled in black; histogram of the hour of events and relative D/N for o) all the
736 events in the grid node, p) all the events in the F1 spatial cluster and q) all the events in
737 the F2 spatial cluster. r) frequency magnitude distributions for all the events in the grid
738 node F from 16 April 2005 to 30 April 2012 (blue circles) and from 1 May 2012 to 30
739 November 2020, red asterisks.

740

741 **Figure 5 A-R.** Spatial and statistical analysis of two grid nodes in the areas labeled as G
742 and H. Grid node in area G in the time period 16 April 2005 - 30 April 2012: a)
743 seismicity map with two spatial clusters, G1 and G2, circled in black; histogram of the
744 hour of events and relative D/N for b) all the events in the grid node, c) all the events in

745 the G1 spatial cluster and d) all the events in the G2 spatial cluster. Grid node in area G
746 in the time period 1 May 2012 - 30 November 2020: f) seismicity map with two spatial
747 clusters, G1 and G2, circled in black; histogram of the hour of events and relative D/N
748 for g) all the events in the grid node, h) all the events in the G1 spatial cluster and i) all
749 the events in the G2 spatial cluster. e) frequency magnitude distributions for all the
750 events in the grid node G from 16 April 2005 to 30 April 2012 (blue circles) and from 1
751 May 2012 to 30 November 2020, red asterisks.

752 Grid node in area H in the time period 16 April 2005 - 30 April 2012: j) seismicity map
753 with two spatial clusters, H1 and H2, circled in black; histogram of the hour of events
754 and relative D/N for k) all the events in the grid node, l) all the events in the H1 spatial
755 cluster and m) all the events in the H2 spatial cluster. Grid node in area H in the time
756 period 1 May 2012 - 30 November 2020: n) seismicity map with two spatial clusters, H1
757 and H2, circled in black; histogram of the hour of events and relative D/N for o) all the
758 events in the grid node, p) all the events in the H1 spatial cluster and q) all the events in
759 the H2 spatial cluster. r) frequency magnitude distributions for all the events in the grid
760 node H from 16 April 2005 to 30 April 2012 (blue circles) and from 1 May 2012 to 30
761 November 2020, red asterisks.

762

763 **Figure 6 A-R.** Spatial and statistical analysis of two grid nodes in the areas labeled as I
764 and J. Grid node in area I in the time period 16 April 2005 - 30 April 2012: a) seismicity
765 map with two spatial clusters, I1 and I2, circled in black; histogram of the hour of events
766 and relative D/N for b) all the events in the grid node, c) all the events in the I1 spatial
767 cluster and d) all the events in the I2 spatial cluster. Grid node in area I in the time

768 period 1 May 2012 - 30 November 2020: e) seismicity map with two spatial clusters, I1
769 and I2, circled in black; histogram of the hour of events and relative D/N for g) all the
770 events in the grid node, h) all the events in the I1 spatial cluster and i) all the events in
771 the I2 spatial cluster. f) frequency magnitude distributions for all the events in the grid
772 node I from 16 April 2005 to 30 April 2012 (blue circles) and from 1 May 2012 to 30
773 November 2020, red asterisks.

774 Grid node in area J in the time period 16 April 2005 - 30 April 2012: j) seismicity map
775 with two spatial clusters, J1 and J2, circled in black; histogram of the hour of events and
776 relative D/N for k) all the events in the grid node, l) all the events in the J1 spatial
777 cluster and m) all the events in the J2 spatial cluster. Grid node in area J in the time
778 period 1 May 2012 - 30 November 2020: n) seismicity map with two spatial clusters, J1
779 and J2, circled in black; histogram of the hour of events and relative D/N for o) all the
780 events in the grid node, p) all the events in the J1 spatial cluster and q) all the events in
781 the J2 spatial cluster. r) frequency magnitude distributions for all the events in the grid
782 node J from 16 April 2005 to 30 April 2012 (blue circles) and from 1 May 2012 to 30
783 November 2020, red asterisks.

784

785 **Figure 7.** Comparison of the frequency magnitude distributions for the five grid nodes
786 in Figures 3 to 6 with low-magnitude events only (B, C, G, I and J) for all the daytime
787 (black circles) and nighttime (grey squares) events for the dataset downloaded via Web
788 Services (event type *earthquake*) from 16 April 2005 to 30 November 2020.

789

790

793

794 **Figure 1 A-D.** Maps of the daytime to night-time ratio (D/N): a) for the time interval
 795 2005-2020 and for the whole dataset downloaded in txt format at

796 <http://terremoti.ingv.it/en/search>. The letters A-J correspond to the excavation districts
797 listed in Table 1. b) for the time interval 16 April 2005 - 30 April 2012, where the events
798 are classified with event type *earthquake*; c) for the time interval 1 May 2012 - 30
799 November 2020, for all the events downloaded in txt format at
800 <http://terremoti.ingv.it/en/search>; d) for the time interval 1 May 2012 - 30 November
801 2020, for all the events downloaded via Web Services selecting the event type
802 *earthquake* only. The maps are computed on a 10-km regularly spaced grid using the
803 events within a 20-km radius from each node.

804

805

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807

808 *Figure 2 A-D.* a-b) Maps of the b-value for the time interval 16 April 2005 - 30

809 November 2020, computed on a 10-km regularly spaced grid using the events within a

810 20-km radius from each node for a) the whole dataset downloaded in txt format at

811 <http://terremoti.ingv.it/en/search> and b) the whole dataset downloaded via Web
812 Services selecting the event type *earthquake* only. c-d) plot of the D/N against the b-
813 value for all the grid nodes adopted in the previous maps for c) the whole dataset
814 downloaded in txt format at <http://terremoti.ingv.it/en/search> and d) the whole
815 dataset downloaded via Web Services selecting the event type *earthquake*.

816

817 **Figure 3 A-P.** Spatial and statistical analysis of four grid nodes in the areas labeled as A-
 818 B-C and E in Figure 1a. a-b) Seismicity maps and histograms of the hours of the events
 819 (c-d) for a grid in area A for, respectively, the events downloaded at
 820 <http://terremoti.ingv.it/en/search> in the period 16 April 2005 - 30 April 2012 and for
 821 the events downloaded via Web Services selecting the event type *earthquake* from 1
 822 May 2012 - 30 November 2020. e-f) Seismicity maps and histograms of the hours of the
 823 events (g-h) for a grid in area B for, respectively, the events downloaded at

824 <http://terremoti.ingv.it/en/search> in the period 16 April 2005 - 30 April 2012 and for
825 the events downloaded via Web Services selecting the event type *earthquake* from 1
826 May 2012 - 30 November 2020. i-j) Seismicity maps and histograms of the hours of the
827 events (k-l) for a grid in area C for, respectively, the events downloaded at
828 <http://terremoti.ingv.it/en/search> in the period 16 April 2005 - 30 April 2012 and for
829 the events downloaded via Web Services selecting the event type *earthquake* from 1
830 May 2012 - 30 November 2020. m-n) Seismicity maps and histograms of the hours of
831 the events (o-p) for a grid in area E for, respectively, the events downloaded at
832 <http://terremoti.ingv.it/en/search> in the period 16 April 2005 - 30 April 2012 and for
833 the events downloaded via Web Services selecting the event type *earthquake* from 1
834 May 2012 - 30 November 2020.

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837 **Figure 4 A-R.** Spatial and statistical analysis of two grid nodes in the areas labeled as D
 838 and F. Grid node in area D in the time period 16 April 2005 - 30 April 2012: a) seismicity
 839 map with two spatial clusters, D1 and D2, circled in black; histogram of the hour of
 840 events and relative D/N for b) all the events in the grid node, c) all the events in the D1
 841 spatial cluster and d) all the events in the D2 spatial cluster. Grid node in area D in the
 842 time period 1 May 2012 - 30 November 2020: f) seismicity map with two spatial
 843 clusters, D1 and D2, circled in black; histogram of the hour of events and relative D/N
 844 for g) all the events in the grid node, h) all the events in the D1 spatial cluster and i) all
 845 the events in the D2 spatial cluster. e) frequency magnitude distributions for all the

846 events in the grid node D from 16 April 2005 to 30 April 2012 (blue circles) and from 1
847 May 2012 to 30 November 2020, red asterisks.

848 Grid node in area F in the time period 16 April 2005 - 30 April 2012: j) seismicity map
849 with two spatial clusters, F1 and F2, circled in black; histogram of the hour of events
850 and relative D/N for k) all the events in the grid node, j) all the events in the F1 spatial
851 cluster and m) all the events in the F2 spatial cluster. Grid node in area F in the time
852 period 1 May 2012 - 30 November 2020: n) seismicity map with two spatial clusters, F1
853 and F2, circled in black; histogram of the hour of events and relative D/N for o) all the
854 events in the grid node, p) all the events in the F1 spatial cluster and q) all the events in
855 the F2 spatial cluster. r) frequency magnitude distributions for all the events in the grid
856 node F from 16 April 2005 to 30 April 2012 (blue circles) and from 1 May 2012 to 30
857 November 2020, red asterisks.

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859

860 **Figure 5 A-R.** Spatial and statistical analysis of two grid nodes in the areas labeled as G
 861 and H. Grid node in area G in the time period 16 April 2005 - 30 April 2012: a)
 862 seismicity map with two spatial clusters, G1 and G2, circled in black; histogram of the
 863 hour of events and relative D/N for b) all the events in the grid node, c) all the events in
 864 the G1 spatial cluster and d) all the events in the G2 spatial cluster. Grid node in area G
 865 in the time period 1 May 2012 - 30 November 2020: f) seismicity map with two spatial
 866 clusters, G1 and G2, circled in black; histogram of the hour of events and relative D/N
 867 for g) all the events in the grid node, h) all the events in the G1 spatial cluster and i) all
 868 the events in the G2 spatial cluster. e) frequency magnitude distributions for all the

869 events in the grid node G from 16 April 2005 to 30 April 2012 (blue circles) and from 1
870 May 2012 to 30 November 2020, red asterisks.

871 Grid node in area H in the time period 16 April 2005 - 30 April 2012: j) seismicity map
872 with two spatial clusters, H1 and H2, circled in black; histogram of the hour of events
873 and relative D/N for k) all the events in the grid node, j) all the events in the H1 spatial
874 cluster and m) all the events in the H2 spatial cluster. Grid node in area H in the time
875 period 1 May 2012 - 30 November 2020: n) seismicity map with two spatial clusters, H1
876 and H2, circled in black; histogram of the hour of events and relative D/N for o) all the
877 events in the grid node, p) all the events in the H1 spatial cluster and q) all the events in
878 the H2 spatial cluster. r) frequency magnitude distributions for all the events in the grid
879 node H from 16 April 2005 to 30 April 2012 (blue circles) and from 1 May 2012 to 30
880 November 2020, red asterisks.

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883 **Figure 6 A-R.** Spatial and statistical analysis of two grid nodes in the areas labeled as I
 884 and J. Grid node in area I in the time period 16 April 2005 - 30 April 2012: a) seismicity
 885 map with two spatial clusters, I1 and I2, circled in black; histogram of the hour of events
 886 and relative D/N for b) all the events in the grid node, c) all the events in the I1 spatial
 887 cluster and d) all the events in the I2 spatial cluster. Grid node in area I in the time
 888 period 1 May 2012 - 30 November 2020: e) seismicity map with two spatial clusters, I1
 889 and I2, circled in black; histogram of the hour of events and relative D/N for g) all the
 890 events in the grid node, h) all the events in the I1 spatial cluster and i) all the events in
 891 the I2 spatial cluster. f) frequency magnitude distributions for all the events in the grid

892 node I from 16 April 2005 to 30 April 2012 (blue circles) and from 1 May 2012 to 30
893 November 2020, red asterisks.

894 Grid node in area J in the time period 16 April 2005 - 30 April 2012: j) seismicity map
895 with two spatial clusters, J1 and J2, circled in black; histogram of the hour of events and
896 relative D/N for k) all the events in the grid node, j) all the events in the J1 spatial
897 cluster and m) all the events in the J2 spatial cluster. Grid node in area J in the time
898 period 1 May 2012 - 30 November 2020: n) seismicity map with two spatial clusters, J1
899 and J2, circled in black; histogram of the hour of events and relative D/N for o) all the
900 events in the grid node, p) all the events in the J1 spatial cluster and q) all the events in
901 the J2 spatial cluster. r) frequency magnitude distributions for all the events in the grid
902 node J from 16 April 2005 to 30 April 2012 (blue circles) and from 1 May 2012 to 30
903 November 2020, red asterisks.

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907 **Figure 7.** Comparison of the frequency magnitude distributions for the five grid nodes
 908 in Figures 3 to 6 with low-magnitude events only (B, C, G, I and J) for all the daytime
 909 (black circles) and nighttime (grey squares) events for the dataset downloaded via Web
 910 Services (event type *earthquake*) from 16 April 2005 to 30 November 2020.